

A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON VISUAL ARTS AND POWERPOINT PRESENTATION (PPT) TO ENHANCE INTERACTIVE TEACHING AND LEARNING

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Abstract

Language is prime and predominant factor to express humans' feelings, thoughts, and information to others. Additionally, it must be elegant and vibrant for rapid flow of communication among the individuals. The present study explores about the importance of using PowerPoint Presentation (PPT) and Visual Arts among the undergraduate literature students in an anonymous university in India. There are (n=50) students taken for study in which (male =25, female =25) in an equal ratio taken for the study. Likewise, (n=10) teachers who handle classes for the above mentioned students are taken into study. PPT has close sumptuous connection with visual arts for splendid and spotless communication. The study reveals that Interactive learning uplifts learners to get redeem from the barriers they undergo in learning an English Language. Questionnaire was given to both teachers and students through e-mail, and by using convenient Sampling Strategy to produce desired results. Here, both teacher and students are shown images by sharing a PPT through e-mail for observation and to kindle the interest of the instructor and the learner. Visual arts combined with technology retain both teachers and the learners to involve in various practical activities that improve the second language fluency. Students clench cognition and attention by engaging themselves through technology based classroom. Thus, the findings were analysed and shown using MS Excel Data Sheet. Moreover, PPT and Visual Arts strengthen Education curriculum and foci on learner centric and promotes flexible and self-directed-learning. The paper centres on visual arts and technology as a key factor to foster interactive learning that assist the learners to abide them to excel in an English language

Keywords: PowerPoint Presentation, Multimedia, Independent Learning, Education, Fluency and Accuracy, Visual Arts and Technology, Communication

INTRODUCTION

Language is meant for communication and expressing an individual thoughts, beliefs, customs, ideas and information to others. According to Bible, it extols the creation and origin of word and language, "In the beginning was the word, and the word was with God, and the word was God" (International Standard Version Bible, 2011, John 1: 1). The verse denotes word is necessary for every language and it must attain its accuracy for efficient communication. People feel easy to convey their thoughts in their native language. But sharing in a second language seems to be hard both for the listener and the conveyer. Bilal Mohd Zakarneh claims that E-learning platform helps to improve English Language skills for non-native speakers of English.(Zakarneh)Likewise, Extramural English(EE)activities like watching TV, playing

games enhances L2 learners good flow of communication.(Uztosun). Additionally, Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL) creates splendid communication among teacher-student and student-student communication through mobile App using Duolingo. (Shortt et al.) Furthermore. Visual arts with the assistance of PPT support learners to carry out effectual communication in second language by upholding technology and interactive learning. The following figure denotes the features of visual arts. (In Figure 1)

Figure 1: Significance of Visual Arts

Research Objectives

The current study analysis about the successive research objectives

- ❖ To delve into visual arts with PPT assistance to upgrade practical learning
- ❖ To strengthen faster communication and sustain active learning
- ❖ To kindle interactive learning among the learners to overcome the fluency barriers in second language
- ❖ To uplift the learners to attain mastery over the English language using technology and visual arts.

Research Aim

The Comparative study conducted at expanding teachers and learners to reach success in enabling effective communication in an English language through the assistance from visual arts and PPT that promotes interactive learning.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

In the present days, massive innovative advancement are taking place in an Educational sector. The advancement of computer technologies and internet makes English language learning in an active manner that assist the second language learners in an effective way.(Erarslan and Arslan)Likewise, technology supports to learn new things. The usage of Moodle, WIKS, Blackboard system sharpens the language efficiency in teaching and learning journey.(Xu) So,

interactive learning assist the learners to involve them in practical activities with builds creative knowledge through visual arts and technology for attaining fluency and accuracy in second language.

Learning English through E-Learning

In the present article, it explains about the pedagogical strategies of learning English through e-learning. In olden days, Chinese people learn English through tape recorders but recently the advancement of internet makes splendid communication among the non-native speakers of English that assist the learners to upgrade their competency and accuracy in a language. The term “direct interest” evokes the learners promote learning in an independent way. It expand the teaching learning process with the assistance from technology and internet. E-learning helps the learners to master in English and improves the language skills of both instructor and the listener. It equips to uplift the learners to become master over an English language.(Cai)

Hybrid Learning

According the article, it states that hybrid learning enables practical learning. It emerges with information and communication technology (ICT) to combine both online and traditional classroom learning. It grasps EFL (English as a foreign language) learners’ attention by watching over YouTube videos that makes teacher as a facilitator and enhances independent learning. However, hybrid learning has few drawbacks in it. It is time consuming and learners find difficult to use the sufficient time in hybrid learning techniques. Though it has negative aspects, it makes learning flexible by using CD-ROMS and latest technologies to share the seminars and lectures for future use. It also the learners to rectify their previous errors and develops language fluency among the second language learners(Klimova and Kacetl)

Benefits of Learning through Technology

In this article, the author depicts the paramount benefits of technology integration among the teachers and the learners. It makes technology based instructions and the objectives foci on learner centred. The teaching learning activities surrounded in a practical environment. Teachers must upgrade their computer literacy to move on with technology integration which assist the individual to kindle their knowledge and interest for learning through technology.(Okojie et al.)

Web Based Language Learning (WBLL) and Speaking Anxiety

In the article, Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) is centred to overcome Foreign Language Speaking Anxiety (FLSA). It is a paramount factor in current educational sector. Speaking skills must be developed in Indonesia which is done through Web Based Language Learning and websites for improving language skills among the learners. The study was undertaken in both quantitative and qualitative aspects by using SPSS in which data was carried out in three way process. It was done through (Pre and post questionnaire, User Experience questionnaire and an interview. It was carried out among both students and teachers. As anxiety is a predominant psychological factor arises in Indonesia, WBLL grows in a massive way along with CALL to overcome FLSA. Here, on analysing the background information, students are

used through technology, yet they were struggling to overcome speaking fear. Both pre, user experience questionnaire along with interviews denotes the anxiety of FLSA and WBL is an alternative factor to attain success in teaching and learning. Furthermore, post questionnaire denotes the positive factors of FLSA in which learners feel comfortable to speak to computers rather than speaking to peer. Websites assist them to enhance and practice speaking skills in a splendid flow of communication. Thus, using WBL and Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR), it is feasible to teach and learn EFL (English as a Foreign Language) through technology in a flexible and independent manner.(Bashori et al.)

L2 Learners with Informal Mobile Language Learning (IMLL) and Person Centred Approach

According to the article, Mobile technologies helps L2 learners to engage in cognitive, metacognitive and affective factors. The research was undertaken based on person centred approach using cluster analysis. (CA). Moreover, Convenient Sampling Strategy was used to produce desired results. The link to an online questionnaire was distributed to 240 students and 238 students taken for research. Despite of the availability of mobile technologies, Informal Mobile Language Learning (IMLL) assists to use person centred approach. The results were carried out based on the questionnaire of IMLL learning experiences and semi structured interviews. The Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA) is applied in the study to explore new groups through bottom up manner. Through clustering procedure, six learner types were identified based on the questionnaire. ANOV as confirmed listening, speaking, reading and writing related activity engagement. Finally, IMLL learning experiences assist china English learning students in a better way.(Peng et al.)

Visual Arts & PowerPoint (PPT) - A Tool to Develop Second Language

The term “Visual Arts” foci on visual images like paint, images, architecture, craft, photographs, film making and so on. Visual arts has close relation with automation and aid to evolve second language which can be shown through PPT slides in an attractive way to both teachers and the learners. ¹ Here, technology occupied paramount position during and after the pandemic. The reason reveals that parents are not convinced to move back to normal education. So technology gives new normal era for both teachers and the students. This new era kindles the interest of the learners.(Nashir and Laili) It stresses on non-vocal communication and kindle learners to frame creative images in their mind that assist to learn the content of the subject in a creative way. Language skills are developed by applying this visual arts techniques along with PPT inside the language classroom.

- ❖ Audio Visual Images
- ❖ Multimedia Presentation

For instance, students are encouraged to watch visual presentation that shows relation to the subject content. It enables them to learn new vocabulary by writing narratives on their own. Short films and can create reviews over it. They are encouraged to learn literature using PPT and images rather on a text book manner. It also helps to learn new vocabulary for the second

language learners. Facebook helps the learners to post visual images and study concepts to develop English language. It is more convenient and flexible for the language teachers.(Karim et al.). Likewise, Language Labs has to be innovated in a better way to implement new visual aids for teaching and learning a second language. The succeeding figure centres on categories of visual arts which can be done through PowerPoint Presentation (PPT). (In Figure 2).

Figure 2: ² Categories of Visual Arts

ICT Enabled Classroom Teaching and Learning

The information and Communication Technology (ICT) has been growing fast in the Educational sector in the recent years. However, research studies shows that ICT enables digital learning tools using Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) and L2 learners are benefited with Asynchronous learning environments which uplift the present adult education. (Bergdahl)Its scope and need has been wider and learners are attached to technology based learning. Since, English is a second language, technology equips learners' attention to improve their language skills to speak elegant and fluent English. ICT makes teaching and learning to create new ideas.(Pardede). Thus, the following figure denotes the ICT skills which assist teachers and learners to use through PPT

Figure 3: ICT skills to improve Computer Literacy

Interactive Learning – to Develop Second Language

English language will develop its fluency with task based activities inside the classroom. The usage of BBC English, You Tube videos and other ICT technologies enhances visual learning.(Minasyan et al.) It enables students to place on interactive sessions between teachers and learners with support of ICT enabled language classroom. Using the visual arts along with PPT, students can be engaged to learn literature in the following activities to upgrade their language fluency. It was shown in the table (Table 1)

Table 1: Learning Literature through Technology Assistance

S.NO	DIVISION ON LITERATURE	USING VISUAL ARTS AND PPT
1.	Poem	Narrative Explanation using Images
2.	Prose	Audio Listening to the text can be played to the learners
3.	Drama	Movies can be played to the learners
4.	One –Act Play	Role play can be enacted in classes from the experts

Here, a sample observation was shown to teachers and students to improve their curiosity. Through mail, two PPT slides were shared to teachers and students. It includes a general topic on “Communication” which was explained through images. The next category was based on poem concept. It includes the following,

- ❖ *Because I Could Not Stop for Death*(Emily Dickinson)
- ❖ *The Road Not Taken*(Robert Frost)
- ❖ *Ode on a Grecian Urn*(John Keats)

According to the views of Huiwei Cai, Chinese people learn English by reading magazines which develop their language vocabulary in a massive way. They record voices and conversation of native speakers in their mobile phones and undergo training by frequent practice. The best way in which Chinese use to develop an English language to reach fluency is using tape recorder which acts as a assistance to enable visual arts to improve the accuracy of the second language.(Cai)Additionally, Pre Service Teachers Professionals (PSTs) shows interest to teach through hybrid space by combining traditional and online delivery content among L2 learners. They rely more on Asynchronous learning tools to promote EFL learning.(Tumelius and Kuure). Moreover, Tourism English assist L2 learners in a better way to teach and learn second language. (Nawamin Prachanant).

Methods and Technologies to Develop Visual Arts in a Language Classroom

Learning Management System (LMS) helps L2 learners to improve language skills and foster communication skills. (Amani Abdelgader Moohammed et al)Likewise, Visual arts has close connection in developing English language for the non-native speakers around the world. Technology is vibrant and energetic for the learners’ and that can be carried to all places. Here, Synchronous Text chat enables L2 learners active which display the language visual to improve the vocabulary of the EFL learners in a better way. (Piyumi Udeshinee et al.) Likewise, Digital Game Based Vocabulary Learning (DGBVL) helps EFL learners to learn new words and its

meanings(semantics) and Morphology(word) through digital games which makes the learners and teachers active..(Rasti-Behbahani and Shahbazi) It is very easy to access and to upgrade learners' skills in English. It permits learners to access internet and acquire self-directed Learning. Rather than foci on old traditional methods, focus was given on technology based learning or Communicative Language Teaching method(CLT) that strengthens EFL learners language accuracy in an massive way.(Yasar Yuzlu and Dikilitas) Thus, the following tables explains few methods and ICT techniques which expand the visual arts in improving an English Language.(In Table 2)

Table 2: ³ Technologies to Enhance Visual Arts

S.NO	Interactive Learning Tools	ICT Technologies
1.	Pre-Recorded Videos	OHP Projectors
2.	Video Calling	ZOOM/SKYPE
3.	Watching Movie Based on Topics	Touch Enabled Laptops
4.	Wireless Presentation Display	Interactive Whiteboards
5.	Listening to a Conversation	Wireless Connections

METHODOLOGY

Questionnaire was used to collect data from the respondents. The research was carried out around the duration of three weeks. Data was collected in an anonymous way. First, observation was done by sharing the PPT to teachers and students respondents for a period of 7 days, later, based on the flexible availability of the respondents, the questionnaire was distributed to them. The questions are framed to show the benefits of PPT and visual arts to enhance interactive learning. It stresses the significance of technology to enhance sumptuous communication in a second language. Close ended type with 5 point Likert scale format was followed to set the questions. The scale ranges from 1-5 in which 1 represents strongly agree, 2 represents agree, 3 represents Neutral, 4 represents disagree and 5 represents strongly disagree.

The questions consisted of two sections. It describes both independent and dependent variables. Personal demography is followed by gender, locality, medium of instruction and some general questions about English language. On the other hand, section B consist of the necessary of PPT and visual arts and which prioritize interactive and practical learning to attain proficiency in an English language.

Selection of Sample Size and Participants

A set of 10 questions were sent to 50 students respondents through e-mail on. On the other hand, the same set of 10 questions were sent to 10 teacher respondents. It was collected back by email itself. The answer expresses both positive and negative responses from the participants. Moreover, positive responses are massive and respondents are active and enthusiastic for practical learning environments.

Sampling Technique

Convenient sampling technique was used to collect data from the participants. It is based on non- profitability sampling technique. Convenient sampling technique is flexible to receive data from the participants related to their proximity and the availability of the respondents.

Analysis of Data

Microsoft Excel Sheet was used to analyse the responses given by the participants. The quantitative data method was followed to show desired results. It was shown through graphs and tables. The analysis foci on the following concepts

- ❖ Interactive Learning through PowerPoint Presentation(PPT)
- ❖ Task Based Practical Learning
- ❖ Visual Arts and Technology

Moreover, before distributing the questionnaire, PPT was shared to the teacher and students based on visual arts and literature for observation the respondents. It was visualized through images of three poems, *Because I Could Not Stop for Death*, *Road Not Taken*, and *Ode on a Grecian Urn*. (Shown in Appendix C)

Appendix C

Literature and Visual Arts

Visual arts assist to develop literature in many ways.

- Poems
- Drama
- Plays
- Poems
- Idiom and Phrases

Likewise, PPT was shared through mail to teacher and students by showing visual images of explaining the meaning of *Communication* to enhance splendid teaching and learning. (Shown in Appendix D)

Appendix D

FINDINGS

The results analysed below prove that learners show keen interest for learning through PPT enabled classroom and visual arts technology that assist and involves them into interactive via practical learning. All these learning techniques are based on the research questions

Learners Background Information

All the participants (including both teachers and students) were belong to undergraduate university teachers and students in India and the teachers who are handling classes for same university undergraduate students. There were 25 boys (50%) and 25 girls (50%) were taken for study. Likewise, there were 5 male teachers (5%) and 5 female teachers (5%) taken for analysis. The results shows that most participants have given their contact details and even email address. But least number of participants failed to have their own email address. Surprisingly, even the few teachers are unaware about having mail id for academic purpose.

Here, both teachers and students have knowledge about technology based teaching and learning. Thus, on using PPT and visual arts in their teaching and learning curriculum, it fosters active learning among students and teachers who upgrade their computer literacy and language fluency using CALL and other technology based learning environments. The teachers and learners personal demographic information are shown in a form of independent variables in (Shown in Appendix A)

Appendix A

Personal Performance Appraisal Data

Independent Variable for the Teachers and the Students

The questionnaire is prepared to get the feedback from the teachers and students for the implementation of visual arts and PPT for the benefit of enhancing effective English language communication to be used in a language classroom to support teaching and learning.

Personal Information

- | | | | | | |
|--|---|----------|----------------------|-----------|----------------------|
| 1. Gender | : | a) Male | <input type="text"/> | b) Female | <input type="text"/> |
| 2. Locality of the College | : | a) Urban | <input type="text"/> | b) Rural | <input type="text"/> |
| 3. Do you listen to English News daily? | | a) Yes | <input type="text"/> | b) No | <input type="text"/> |
| 4. Do you prefer Interactive Learning? | | a) Yes | <input type="text"/> | b) No | <input type="text"/> |
| 5. Are you interested in learning through
Slide Presentation (PPT)? | | a) Yes | <input type="text"/> | b) No | <input type="text"/> |
| 6. Are you interested in learning through
Visual arts | | a) Yes | <input type="text"/> | b) No? | <input type="text"/> |

Analysis Based on Dependent Variables of Students

The questionnaire was given to both teacher and students to analyse the basic interest and knowledge of the respondents. The results were proven through Excel data sheet based on the responses given in the questionnaire. (Shown in Appendix B)

Appendix B

Visual Arts

- Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) with visual arts to learn difficult tasks in an easy way and grasps the learners' attention effectively
 - Strongly Agree
 - Agree
 - Neutral
 - Strongly Disagree
 - Disagree

2. Visual Arts Classroom enables to use picture and animation during Online and Offline Classes.
 - a) Strongly Agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Strongly Disagree
 - e) Disagree
3. Visual Arts supports students to learn through Audio and Video Aids that enhances quick Learning.
 - a) Strongly Agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Strongly Disagree
 - e) Disagree
4. Visual Arts kindle Computer Literacy of the both teacher and the students.
 - a) Strongly Agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Strongly Disagree
 - e) Disagree
5. Multimedia Learning helps the learners to learn new vocabulary words in an easy way.
 - a) Strongly Agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Strongly Disagree
 - e) Disagree

PowerPoint Presentation (PPT)

6. PowerPoint Presentation helps to connect both online and offline classes together.
- a) Strongly Agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Strongly Disagree
 - e) Disagree
7. Learning with PowerPoint enables interest of the students and teachers to learn and teach new things.
- a) Strongly Agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Strongly Disagree
 - e) Disagree
8. Teaching through PowerPoint covers over crowded classroom and helps for future use.
- a) Strongly Agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Strongly Disagree
 - e) Disagree
9. PowerPoint is virtually use anywhere that reduces the speaking fear of the teachers and the students.
- a) Strongly Agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Strongly Disagree
 - e) Disagree

10. PowerPoint Presentation supports to develop the listening skills of the both teacher and the students.

- a) Strongly Agree
- b) Agree
- c) Neutral
- d) Strongly Disagree
- e) Disagree

Collaborative Learning

Massive number of participants (36%) strongly agreed that visual arts enhances collaborative learning and few number of participants (33%) also accepted collaborative learning. Additionally, Neutral responses are shown from (14%) of participants. However, pessimistic responses are drawn in which (12%) of participants disagreed about enabling collaborative learning through visual arts and (5%) of participants strongly denied the above concept. (Figure 4)

Figure 4: Visual Arts Enhances Collaborative Learning

Visual Arts and Active Learning

Majority of participants (36%) strongly agree that visual arts assist to grasp innovative things and (33%) of participants agree the concept. Furthermore, (14%) of participants responded neutrally. Moreover, (12%) of participants rejected it by disagreeing that learners fail to grasp innovative things and (5%) of participants strongly disagree that learners are not active to grasp new things through visual arts. (Figure 5)

Figure 5: Learners Are Active To Grasp New Things Using Visual Arts

Content Sharing and Interactive Learning

Most of the participants (41%) strongly agree that interactive learning assist content sharing in a flexible way. Likewise, (29%) of participants agreed about leaning through interactive sessions. (13%) of participants responded for content sharing and interactive learning. However, (9%) of participants shows negative responses by disagreeing it. Finally, (8%) of participants rejected by strongly disagreeing that content sharing not effective through interactive learning. (Figure 6)

Figure 6: Content Sharing Is Enabled Through Interactive Learning

Technology and long term memory

Most of the participants (36%) strongly agreed that long term memory is possible through technology and (33%) of participants agreed and supported technology based learning. But neutral responses are shown from (14%) of participants. In addition to (12%) of participants neglected that long memory is not much effective through technology and (5%) of participants also strongly disagreed about technology and long term memory from the learners.(Figure 7)

Figure 7: Technology based learning retain long term memory of the learners

Peer Interaction and Interactive Learning

Majority of participants (35%) strongly agreed that peer interactive is active among interactive learning and (27%) of participants agreed it. Likewise, neutral responses raised from (15%) of participants. Moreover, (18%) of participants neglected about interactive learning which kindles interactive learning and (5%) of participants strongly disagreed it. (Figure 8)

Figure 8: Peer interaction is kindled through interactive learning

Multitasking and Learning

Multitasking is possible through visual arts which is strongly agreed by (30%) of participants and (20%) of participants are also agreed positively about multitasking and interactive learning. (15%) of participants shows neutral responses on it. Moreover, (15%) of participants disagreed and denied the concept and (20%) of participants strongly disagreed it. (Figure 9)

Figure 9: Multitasking Is Possible Through Arts and Technology

Benefits of Visual Arts and Animation

Visual arts enables picture and animation learning and it is strongly agreed by 35% of participants and 25% of participants agreed it. Additionally 20% of participants responded neutrally. However, 10% of participants disagreed the above statement of learning through visual arts and again a 10% of participants strongly agreed the above concept of learning. (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Visual Arts Archives to Learn Using Picture, Coloured Text and Graphics

Task Based and Practical Learning

Practical learning is supported and strongly agreed by 35% of participants and 30% of participants agreed it. Likewise, 15% of participants gave neutral responses for the below statement. Furthermore, 10% of participants disagreed the statement and finally 10% of participants strongly disagreed for the concept that communication is flexible through practical learning. (Figure 11)

Figure 11: Learners' communication is flexible through practical learning

Multimedia and Vocabulary Learning

It is noted that learning through multimedia and visual arts develops vocabulary and this statement is strongly agreed by 33% of participants and 30% of participants agreed this declaration. However, 13% of participants shows neutral responses for the statement. Likewise, 12% of participants disagreed the concept and again 12% of participants strongly disagreed the statement. (Figure 12)

Figure 12: Multimedia with Visual Learning Assist to Improve Second Language Vocabulary

Language Fluency through Visual Presentation

Majority of the participants around 32% strongly agreed for (visual presentation assist to attain fluency and 28% of participants agreed it. Furthermore, 16% of participants responded neutrally for the statement about attaining fluency through visual learning. Moreover, 12% of participants disagreed the following statement and 12% of participants strongly disagreed the statement. (Figure 13)

Figure 13: Fluency Is Attained Easily Through Visual Presentation

RESULTS BASED ON THE RESPONSES OF THE TEACHER

Majority of participants (35%) accepted for learning through CALL and collaborative teaching. They are interested to use PPT with multimedia presentation with (35%) of least participants agree to teach their subject content. As the teachers have less knowledge about technology based teaching environments, they show (10%) of participants in a neutral manner. On the other hand, it is interested to receive negative responses from the few teacher participants of (10%) who disagree the concept of learning through PPT and finally again (10%) of participants strongly disagree to teach and learn through visual arts.(Figure 14)

Figure 14: PPT and Visual Arts Teaching Among the Teacher Respondents

DISCUSSION ON THE COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF TEACHERS AND STUDENTS

The study aimed at analysing and investigating (1) Importance of PPT and visual arts among EFL learner. (2) The usage Of ICT enabled classroom to kindle interest among the learners to induce flexible and Self- Directed Learning. (3) The effects of PPT and visual arts to teach and learn literature in an effective splendid way. The participants of both teachers and the students were analysed through MS Excel data sheet to produce desired results. In the study, the focus centres on developing English among EL learners through the assistance of technology like PPT and visual arts. The comparative study results is done through questionnaire on PPT and visual arts among teachers and the students. The results were carried out in an anonymous Indian university for 50 student respondents and 10 teacher respondents. The results supported that in a traditional classroom, teachers taught lesson in a one way communication with old blackboard teaching. Even students were passive to listen to the boring lectures. In addition to technology centred classroom, students practice interactive sessions and make class livelier. Speaking gives predominant position to enhance interactive teaching and learning that assist to improve communication among EFL learners

The current study seeks to find prospective solution to teach and learn English Education through technology like PPT and visual arts among non-native speakers of English. The study reveals that both the teachers and students feel comfortable and active through technology assisted classroom environment. On analysing 50 students (including both male and female, most of the participants (70%) were given positive responses for learning through visual arts and PPT. Likewise, 10 teachers were taken for study in which all the teacher respondents around(70%) given splendid positive responses that shown that they are kindled to teach through technology. Here, (10%) of participants from teachers and students show neutral responses due to the lack of practice undertaken by using the technologies. However, on analysing, the negative responses, it was shown that only (20%) of least respondents disagree to learn through PPT and visual arts. The reason proves that, these respondents of both teachers and the students has lack of computer literacy and they fail to have adequate knowledge in using the above technologies. They are abide to traditional classroom teaching and learning. Finally, Comparative analyses proves that technology acts a paramount assistance to EFL learners to grasp the language fluency and mater in communication and language skills.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Regarding the paper limitations, it sets path for present research to be acknowledged.

First, the importance of PPT and visual arts are described to improve and upgrade the language fluency among the EFL learners. The future research to concentrate on learning using Interactive Whiteboards among the EFL learners

Second limitations the questionnaire was distributed to both teachers and students in an anonymous Indian university to identify the interest of interactive learning. So future research can be undertaken on either complete Hybrid or Blended teaching and learning.

Furthermore, final limitation regards the result of the data analysis using MS Excel data sheet based on Convenient Sampling Strategy. Technology based classroom kindle to develop practical and active learning among the EFL learners. Thus, the future research must involve in concentrating in each language skills (Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing) and also foci on teaching learning through advanced educational technologies.

CONCLUSION

Teaching and Learning second language uplifts learners' competency and acquires mastery and fluency over a language. (Perwi Darmajanti et.al)Autonomy, Curiosity, motivation are combined together for readiness to online learning to enhance language competency and for effective L2 communication(Paradowski and Jelińska). The effect of multimedia learning using text, animation, images promotes both teachers and learners to acquire new vocabulary words for practicing L2 teaching and learning.(Teng)⁴ PowerPoint Presentation (PPT) and Visual Arts is a fabulous to develop second language among EFL learners India. It assist both teachers and learners to attain good vocabulary context among teachers and students for the good rapid flow of teaching and learning. It is also effective through Blended learning in which students learn through distance education that effectively mould positive learning methods and gain splendid feedback among the individuals(Tayebinik).⁵ English makes learning active and interactive with the support of new and latest technologies to attain flawless and rapid flow of communication. It enhances good language competencies in acquiring mastery over the language. It also has good scope over the field of literature, arts and humanities. Likewise, technologies with virtual environments enhances to improve productive and receptive skills of English.(Hercik et al.). Thus, learning through visual arts using PPT delve into interactive learning with technologies that develop English language in a better way.

Footnotes

1. The studies proves that COVID -19(Corona Virus) showed a splendid change in educational system through technology based classroom
2. The data in figure 2 foci on learning through visual arts which enhances active education among the L2 learners.
3. Additionally, The data in figure 3 acts as a supporting factor to enable the benefits of using PPT and Visual Arts for the effectiveness of teaching and learning.
4. Likewise, PPT removes speaking anxiety among L2 learners and improves faster communication through ICT enabled classroom.
5. Moreover, technology acts as an emerging assistance tool to promote English language globally.

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Data Availability Statement

There are no Data Availability Statement used here.

Disclosure Statement

The Author Report That There Are No Competing Interests To Declare.

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